

Evaluation of online learning implementation as learning culture change in pandemic time

Parwita Setya Wardhani^{1,*}, Rika Yulianti¹, Annisa Silfia², M Fahrudin Ali Fikri³, Agus Hendrawan⁴, Novita Sari³ and Erick Fajar Subhekti³

¹ Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

² Stikes DARUL AZHAR Batulicin, Kalimantan Selatan, Indonesia.

³ Airlangga University Postgraduate, Indonesia.

⁴ Brawijaya University Postgraduate, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 14(02), 680–685

Publication history: Received on 24 April 2022; revised on 31 May 2022; accepted on 02 June 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.14.2.0487>

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has changed the learning culture from offline learning to online. Various online learning methods are carried out and adapted to conditions in the existing environment. From the implementation of this change in learning culture, it is necessary to evaluate its sustainability, especially the problems faced during the implementation of online learning. This research was conducted to see how the implementation of online learning in the Postgraduate Program at Lambung Mangkurat University. By apply a qualitative method in this study, we involve the competent informants being the Head of the Study Program, Lecturer and students in two study programs, namely the Biology Education and Basic Principles and Environmental Ethics (PSDAL). The main data is obtained from 6 informants and available secondary data. The results of the evaluation can be seen from the readiness of human resources, in this case lecturers and students are ready and have adapted well. E-Learning is re-integrated with the academic system so that data from the learning process in E-learning is reported directly to the campus academic system. Blended learning method one of the learning models that can be applied through the use of technology-based media used in the two study programs. This online learning has a positive impact on students with a higher level of independence, as well as for lecturers with a higher level of creativity in delivering material. Meanwhile, the obstacles to online learning are signal interference and quota fees (although the campus has provided a subsidy of IDR 200,000/month, which is still not enough).

Keywords: Blended Learning; Covid-19 Pandemic; Education; Online Learning

1. Introduction

Understanding the phenomenon of courage-based education has become a critical concern recently. In the early 2000s, this discussion of courageous education had begun. Until it became a serious conversation at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. This phenomenon is evidenced by the very drastic use of the Zoom Meeting application up to 3000% in 2020 [1]. Its users also vary, from elementary school students to college students.

This change has been debated in previous research by experts. one that is debated is the concept of quality bold learning [2]. According to her, bold learning is a search for quality and user satisfaction. In addition, the use of technology in the learning process still needs to be questioned because there are still unproven experiments, especially at the university

* Corresponding author: Parwita Setya Wardhani
Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

level [3]. Because the main problem in bold learning is the development, development, and future of technology supporting sustainable learning [4].

Much of the skepticism of these experts is based on questions about the quality and effectiveness of bold learning. The development of learning from spawned many standards and frameworks to develop and promote them [5]. The currently available frameworks provide a general basis for making high-quality programs, but will not be specific enough for high-level assessments to organize and ensure a comprehensive quality education program [6]. The distinguishing feature of the new framework on bold learning is to develop the learning design of academic staff and to encourage greater involvement across the university [7].

Bold learning can be called a transformative process related to developing appropriate lifelong learning capacities in students [8]. The advantages of bold learning are considered to be cheaper than traditional learning models, such as trips for teachers and students plus the time they book becomes lower.

Another advantage is the convenience, standardized learning process, independent learning, and various other content [9]. And in bold learning, the content of the material and the design structure of the technology are considered equally important for the learner and the architecture [10].

Brave learning is the main method in the process of delivering knowledge to students. As in the results of research by experts, the learning process shows its advantages and disadvantages. The advantage is that students can access or participate in learning from anywhere and of course it has an impact on the cost-effective expenses of the students. The drawback is that many students encounter technological barriers. So that it is again emphasized how to maintain the quality of courageous learning.

To validate the bold learning framework, it is necessary to review its effectiveness, input from experts, empirical research, surveys, develop pilot projects, and describe them in various case studies [11]. The shift towards accountability in learning in the higher education sector has had an impact on the provision of distance education library services [12]. Because quality assurance and quality improvement processes ensure a comprehensive coverage of the factors that affect student learning experiences [13]. So that this research is present as an effort to answer these challenges, with the formulation of the problem: "How is the evaluation of the implementation of the online teaching and learning process as an effort to ensure the quality of learning?"

2. Theoretical Foundation

2.1. Learning

Learning is essentially a process of regulating, organizing the environment around students, so that they can grow and encourage them to carry out the learning process. Trianto in [14] learning is a complex aspect of activity and cannot be fully explained. In simple terms, learning can be interpreted as a product of continuous interaction between development and life experience.

According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education system, that learning is a process of interaction between educators and students and learning resources that take place in a learning environment, while Hamalik in [15] states that learning is a combination that includes human elements (students and teachers), materials (boards, chalk, books, and learning tools), facilities (clear space, audio-visual) and processes influence each other to achieve learning objectives.

So in simple terms it can be said that learning is an interaction activity carried out by teachers to students with the aim that students have knowledge, including providing learning materials, knowledge information, activities guiding students, and presenting so that students can achieve the goals of achieving the goals that have been set, by supporting facilities and materials that are useful in facilitating the learning process.

2.2. Various Online Learning Methods

2.2.1. Internet e-learning

Internet e-learning is an acronym for 'in the network', which is an activity carried out with a bold system that utilizes the internet network. According to [16] bold learning is a program for organizing online learning classes to reach a massive and broad target group.

Thorne in [17] bold learning is a learning program that uses multimedia technology, virtual classes, CD ROM, video streaming, voice messages, email and telephone conferences, online text animation and online video streaming, meanwhile Rosenberg in [18], that e-learning refers to the use of internet technology to find solutions that can improve knowledge and skills.

According to Permendikbud No. 109/2013, distance education is a teaching and learning process that is carried out remotely through the use of communication media, and with advances in information and communication technology it is possible to implement and bring changes and progress in various sectors, one of which is in the education sector. This learning can be controlled massively with an unlimited number of participants, besides that learning can be accessed anytime and anywhere there is no time limit in the use of learning materials.

From some of the definitions above, it can be said that bold learning or e-learning is a learning that utilizes technology by using the internet where the learning process is not done face-to-face but uses electronic media that makes it easier for students to learn anytime and anywhere.

2.2.2. Mobile learning

During the pandemic, the world of education, especially universities, began to use mobile learning applications as a solution to support distance learning. This is one of the important issues regarding the readiness of universities to implement new systems, such as mobile learning applications. Determining the most important aspects of readiness to use mobile learning is a key step to adopting the system in an effective and efficient manner [19]. Learning methods that use cell phones, methods used to complement learning, and provide opportunities for students to study or repeat the desired lesson anytime and anywhere. This is an alternative method because almost everyone uses an android-based smartphone, and learning is also very flexible to carry and use, unlike laptops which require a certain space and handling.

2.2.3. Quantum learning method

That is a learning method that can strengthen and sharpen memory, with a fun method and adapted to students' conditions. The interactions in it include elements that will affect student success [20].

2.3. Google Class

Google Classroom is a role that helps help save time, keep organized and improve communication with students. Google Classroom helps teachers create and organize assignments quickly, provide input efficiently and communicate more easily, while also helping students organize assignments on Google Drive, complete and submit them.

This tool combines google docs, drive and Gmail, not only efficient and reduces paper loss, but makes it easier to check those who have not submitted assignments and provide real-time feedback to each student.

2.4. Corona Virus 19

SARS-CoV-2/Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an encased, constructive sense, single-stranded RNA virus similar to severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) coronavirus [21]. Viruses are the cause of the emergence of diseases that occur in humans and animals, Corona viruses infect humans, especially respiratory tract infections. The coronavirus disease – 2019 (Covid-19) is a new type of corona virus that was discovered in December 2019 in Wuhan City, China. This virus has a virus that differs from bat coronavirus DNA by about 85%, genetically SARS-Cov and Mers-Cov, 60-140 nm, in the phyllo elliptic genus and is pleomorphic, and this virus was found after 96 hours in respiratory epithelial cells. man. '

So, it can be said that Covid-19 is a new type of virus whose characteristics are different from the corona virus in humans that was previously discovered. This virus defends itself well and survives for a long time, so it can experience a very fast spread.

3. Research method

The research method used in this study is a qualitative case study method. Case studies are used to explore a phenomenon in depth, especially when the boundaries between the phenomena are still unclear. The data collection for a case study method is usually done by combining archives, interviews, questionnaires and observations [22]. We used several competent informants, namely the Head of the Study Program, Lecturer and Student in the Biology Education study program and PSDAL. The two study programs are located at the Lambung Mangkurat University postgraduate

program in South Kalimantan. The secondary data source was E-Learning documentation as an initial step of this research.

4. Result and Discussion

Lambung Mangkurat University Postgraduate Program, Faculty of Biology Education. Conducts online learning for all undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral study programs. The student as one of the informants stated that learning on campus was bold and captivating.

The SIMARI ULM information system is an Integrated Lambung Mangkurat University Information System, where all applications are interconnected. With the hope that SIMARI can realize a well-managed ULM Information System. The learning process at Lambung Mangkurat University (ULM) is carried out using blended learning. And learning is done boldly during a pandemic. All lecturers actively provide lectures and assignments for students. In Table 1, it provides information that the fulfilment of lecturers is in accordance with needs, technically learning is done by zoom meet (students are required to be on camera) and materials, assignments, attendance and exams are in E-learning. The academic system and E-Learning are reintegrated with the academic system so that data from the learning process in E-learning is reported directly to the campus academic system.

The main obstacle to online learning is signal interference and the cost for the quota (even though the campus has provided a subsidy of IDR 200,000/month) is still lacking. It is more felt when this error signal occurs during the exam, which results in not being able to finish the exam well or even not being able to take the exam.

Table 1 Factors that are the main causes that affect quality

College factor	Biology	PSDA
Man	The number of lecturers is 11 with functional positions of lector-1person, head lector-6person, and professor- 4person. Lecturers are well responsible. Students follow the learning process with discipline.	The number of lecturers is 110 with the functional position of Doctor-8person and professors-2person Lecturers are well responsible. Students follow the learning process with discipline.
Ingredients	Lecture material, midterm exam (UTS) and final exams (UAS) questions as well as assignments, and attendance, grades	Lecture material, midterm exam (UTS) and final exams (UAS) questions as well as assignments, and attendance, grades
Machine	SIMARI as an integrated information system E-Learning as a means of courageous learning	SIMARI as an integrated information system E-Learning as a means of courageous learning
Method	Blended learning-One of the learning models that can be applied through the use of technology-based media is the blended learning model. [23] Learning that combines or combines various web-based technologies, to achieve educational goals. In other words Thorne, 2013 in [24] Mixed learning from e-learning and multimedia technologies, such as video streaming, virtual classes, online text animations combined with other forms of classroom training. Simply put Graham, 2005 in [25] as learning that combines online learning with face-to-face (face-to-face learning).	Blended learning-One of the learning models that can be applied through the use of technology-based media is the blended learning model. [23] Learning that combines or combines various web-based technologies, to achieve educational goals. In other words Thorne, 2013 in [24] Mixed learning from e-learning and multimedia technologies, such as video streaming, virtual classes, online text animations combined with other forms of classroom training. Simply put Graham, 2005 in [25] as learning that combines online learning with face-to-face (face-to-face learning).

Source: processed field data

During the learning process students expressed satisfaction and could understand the material presented by the lecturer. Online learning has a positive impact on students where their independence is higher, as well as for lecturers

with higher creativity. Lecturers to be able to give their presentations so that they can be felt by students even though the conditions are far away.

5. Managerial Implication

The results of this study enrich information related to teaching management that can be applied during the covid-19 pandemic where the prohibition on holding face-to-face lectures to prevent the spread of the covid-19 virus is addressed by online teaching which requires a fairly complex preparation process and procedure. Apart from the disturbing problems related to signal strength for certain areas as well as the costs that must be incurred during online teaching, this is useful information for policy improvement from related institutions and the government.

6. Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the culture of learning at all levels of education. Distance is the only option for learning the learning process. Ability development, creativity both lecturers and students are needed for the purpose of achieving the learning process

Post-graduate at the University of Lambung Mangkurat, able to adapt to the conditions of this Covid-19 pandemic, the learning process boldly went smoothly. Although obstacles still exist, such as quotas which are perceived as expensive, and dependence on signals is very high. Human resource development must still be maintained and carried out due to sudden changes or changing the culture in the campus environment, the result of which is the readiness of human resources to make changes. The estimated transition from the COVID-19 pandemic to endemic in the next few months will also change the culture that we have been through for more than two years with the conditions of the Pandemic.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Wyld D. Zooming Ahead : The Explosive Growth of Zoom During the Pandemic 2020.
- [2] McLoughlin C. Perspectives on the quality of online education. Qual. Educ. a Distance, Springer; 2003, p. 273–80.
- [3] Oliver R. Quality assurance and e-learning: blue skies and pragmatism. ALT-J 2005;13:173–87.
- [4] McLoughlin C, Visser T. Quality e-learning: Are there universal indicators. Sixt. ODLAA Bienn. Forum Conf. Proceedings, Sustain. Qual. Learn. Environ. Canberra, vol. 13, 2003.
- [5] Stewart BL, Goodson CE, Miertschin SL, Norwood ML, Ezell S. Online student support services: A case based on quality frameworks. J Online Learn Teach 2013;9:290.
- [6] Mariasingam MA, Hanna DE. Benchmarking quality in online degree programs status and prospects. Online J Distance Learn Adm 2006;9.
- [7] Ireland J, Correia HM, Griffin TM. Developing quality in e-learning: a framework in three parts. Qual Assur Educ 2009.
- [8] Holt D, Challis D. From policy to practice: One university's experience of implementing strategic change through wholly online teaching and learning. Australas J Educ Technol 2007;23.
- [9] Strother J, Alford R. E-learning for corporate training: A review of the literature. EdMedia+ Innov Learn 2001:1825–7.
- [10] Agariya AK, Singh D. e-Learning quality: Scale development and validation in Indian context. Knowl Manag E-Learning An Int J 2012;4:500–17.

- [11] Inglis A. Approaches to the validation of quality frameworks for e-learning. *Qual Assur Educ* 2008.
- [12] Cother C, Parnell S. Quality assurance and models of service in an environment of change. *J Libr Adm* 2002;37:189–206.
- [13] Inglis A. Assessing the need for a quality framework designed specifically for managing the provision of online distance education in developing countries 2010.
- [14] Pane A, Dasopang MD. Belajar dan pembelajaran. *Fitrah J Kaji Ilmu-Ilmu Keislami* 2017;3:333–52.
- [15] Fakhrurrazi F. Hakikat pembelajaran yang efektif. *At-Tafkir* 2018;11:85–99.
- [16] Bilfaqih Y, Qomarudin MN. *Esensi Penyusunan Materi Pembelajaran Daring*. Deepublish; 2015.
- [17] Kuntarto E. Keefektifan model pembelajaran daring dalam perkuliahan bahasa Indonesia di perguruan tinggi. *Indones Lang Educ Lit* 2017;3:99–110.
- [18] Alimuddin A, Nadjib M. Intensitas Penggunaan E-learning dalam Menunjang Pembelajaran Mahasiswa Program Sarjana (S1) di Universitas Hasanuddin. *KAREBA J Ilmu Komun* 2015:387–98.
- [19] Almaiah MA, Al-Otaibi S, Lutfi A, Almomani O, Awajan A, Alsaaidah A, et al. Employing the TAM Model to Investigate the Readiness of M-Learning System Usage Using SEM Technique. *Electronics* 2022;11:1259.
- [20] Ahmadi A, Prasetya JT. *Strategi Belajar Mengajar*. Pustaka Setia Bandung; 2013.
- [21] Zhang T, Wu Q, Zhang Z. Probable pangolin origin of SARS-CoV-2 associated with the COVID-19 outbreak. *Curr Biol* 2020;30:1346–51.
- [22] Yin RK. *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. Los Angeles, UK Sage 2018.
- [23] Driscoll M. Blended learning: Let's get beyond the hype. *E-Learning* 2002;1:1–4.
- [24] DAKHI O, JAMA J, IRFAN D. Blended learning: a 21st century learning model at college. *Int J Multi Sci* 2020;1:50–65.
- [25] Bencheva N. Learning styles and e-learning face-to-face to the traditional learning. *Научни Трудове На Русенския Университет* 2010;49:63–7.